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Macroeconomic, Structural and Social Policy Priorities for the Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste (RDTL) with Visa Exemption for the State of Indonesia

(Case study: Cross-border Service Post RDTL and the State of Indonesia)

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ABSTRACT

"The implementation of the political policies of the east timor government regarding visa waiver for Indonesian citizens in 2019" (case study of postal service cross border mota 'ain, kabupaen belu, tasifeto district east, village of silawan). "Results, studies of political science, department of social and political sciences, nusa cendana university" In the implementation of the free visa policy for Indonesian citizens, it is either a mutual policy or a high school acceptance made by the east timor government to the Indonesian government, which, under the 2016 ban on visa free to visit foreign citizens, The government at east timor in bilateral relations has made a visa - free policy for Indonesian citizens based on a government resolution or resolvable coes at government number 25/2019. The type of visa that is exempt is the type of tourism visa or tourist visa. a tourist visa can be valid for 30 days and can be extended for 60 days. The purpose of this visa-free policy is to support TimorLeste's economy in the tourism sector and can be recognized internationally. Among others by the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). The qualitative method of judging, the study is carried out for 3 months in February 2020. Cba said cgi would be able to improve cbi's decision to increase its investment in the second quarter of 2007. The research informant has nine people. Sive intelligence technique for informants. The result of research that the east timor government is pursuing a policy is that it can pay attention and optimize the implementation of a free visa policy by performing socialization, by conducting referrals, conducting supervision and by the Economic, Social and Political Environment.

Keywords: *Macroeconomic, Structural and Social Policy Priorities, Visa Exemption*

Introduction

In this modern era, the world is required to follow the changes that occur in society. Especially as a result of revolutionary changes in the fields of technology, information, communication and transportation. Following these changes, international issues have also become very broad. At first the study of international relations was only

concerned with high politics issues such as war and the economy. But in reality, nowadays, everything is changing. The study of international relations is also dominated by law and politics issues, such as social and cultural issues. In fact, it does not even reach these issues, but at this time international relations are also dominated by inter-

actions between transnational actors, which from time to time are higher than official relations between countries.

According to Kalevi Holsti (2017: 3) in the book *Fundamentals of International Relations*, said that the Study of International Relations covers a complex whole regarding the cultural, economic, legal, military, political, and social relations of all countries as well as the elements of the population and population. their entities and continued with

the thoughts of Stephanie Lawson who said that international relations are relations between state-based actors that cross state borders. Thus, international relations are determined from various aspects and perspectives within a country whether in the social, economic, political or in this case geographical location and a country can also build good international relations if the country has become an independent country in all aspects and fields.

Furthermore, in the journal *Enforcement of Visa-free Visits and Its Relation to the Presence of illegal foreign workers from China who have the potential to threaten the Sovereignty of the Indonesian State (2017:4)*, there is a principle in international law which says "par in parem non great jurisdictionem", which means that every country have the same and equal status, no country shall exercise its jurisdiction over another country without the consent of the other country. In connection with the independence and sovereignty of the state, the journal *Montevideo Convention in 1933* said that a state must have (four) elements, namely:

- 1. Permanent people;***
- 2. Fixed area or area;***
- 3. Government;***
- 4. Ability to establish relations with other countries.***

Timor Leste is one of the countries that has fulfilled the four elements, this is proven by the results of the referendum on August 30, 1999 under the supervision of the United Nations Mission in East Timor (UNAMET) which has ushered the territory of Timor Leste into a new history. After the handover of full sovereignty by UNTAET (United Nation Transition in East Timor) to the government of Timor Leste on 20 May 2002, the people of Timor Leste organized the government as an independent country. International recognition of independence has further strengthened its position as a sovereign State, with the official title *Republica Democratica de Timor Leste (RDTL)*.

As an independent country, Timor Leste must be responsible for the welfare of the people and fully maintain domestic political stability for long-term national security. Political stability and national resilience are two very important things to strive for as a

new country. Timor Leste has a special priority to grow, maintain and develop political stability and national security. A newly independent country is prone to conflict within a country, as well as Timor Leste. Improving the national condition becomes the main task in addition to other tasks.

In various international activities, Timor Leste has participated with associations or groups of countries that can be followed, one of which is the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) to build partnerships in the region, apart from cooperative relationships with associations of other countries. Southeast Asia (ASEAN) East Timor is geographically part of the South Pacific region. Although Timor Leste is often considered part of Southeast Asia, Timor Leste itself has a role as an observer for countries in the South Pacific Region. So that with the sovereignty possessed by Timor Leste, it can also build cooperative relations with countries in the South Pacific Region. How-

ever, it cannot be denied that the sovereignty of a country will work well if the country can build cooperative relations with neighboring countries. In order for the function of the state to run properly, the state cannot separate itself from other countries. Timor Leste is classified as the youngest country in the world that has become independent and has an area that is not much different from Indonesia. Because the location of the region is not much different from Indonesia, either by land, sea or air. The country of Timor Leste is limited by several geographical features and is directly adjacent to other countries such as:

1. North: directly adjacent to the Banda Strait, Weter Island and Alor Island in Indonesia,
2. South: Borders with Australia and Timor Strait
3. West: bordering the Kupang district of East Nusa Tenggara in Indonesia
4. East: bordering the Leti archipelago in Indonesia

In accordance with the boundaries listed above, the boundaries of the State of Timor Leste are dominated by the border with the state of Indonesia. In relation to Indonesia, the State of Timor Leste previously did not apply VISA free for visitors from the Indonesian people who wish to go to Timor Leste, both in terms of traveling, trading, as well as in building cooperation between the two countries. So that citizens who want to visit Timor Leste are subject to visa payments in accordance with the rules that have been set.

Based on Timor-Leste Law No. 11 of 2017 concerning Immigration and Asylum, Visas are divided into several types, as follows:

1. (Tourist/Business Visit): Valid for 30 days and can be extended at the Timor-Leste Immigration Office in Dili up to a maximum of 90 days. For an extension of

stay for 30 days, a fee of US\$.35.00 (thirty five US Dollars) will be charged and for a stay of 30-60 days a fee of US\$.75.00 (seventy-five US Dollars) will be charged.

2. (Transit): Valid for 3 days (72 hours) at a cost of US\$.20.00 (twenty US Dollars) and cannot be extended.

3. (Learning): Applications must be submitted prior to departure to Timor-Leste through the Timor-Leste Representative Office in Indonesia. Visa can be granted for 1 (one) time or multiple trips (maximum stay period is a year) and is subject to a fee of US\$.40.00 (forty US Dollars).

4. (Social-cultural/Sports/Media coverage): Applications must be submitted prior to departure to Timor-Leste through the Timor-Leste Representative Office in Indonesia.

5. Work permit/visa: application must be submitted prior to departure to Timor Leste through Timor Leste's representative office abroad/Indonesia.

6. Residence Permit: divided into Temporary Stay Permit, Residence Permit for family reunions, permanent or permanent residence permit.

Since September 26, 2019, there has been a VISA-free application for Indonesian citizens who wish to go to Timor Leste. As stated by the Indonesian Embassy in Dilli in Press Relations, the government of Timor Leste has released VISA for ordinary visits to the Indonesian people. The decision is contained in Government Resolution or Resolucoes do Governo Number 25/2019.

B. Theoretical Foundation

The implementation of public policy that we are currently studying is the third generation (Lester and Stewart Jr. 2000; Pulzl and Treib 2007). The first generation developed in the 1970s to the early 1980s, where the implementation model developed was top-down theories (also called top-downers or forward-mapping). While the second

generation developed in the 1980s to 1985 which developed bottom-up up theorist (bottom-uppers or backward-mapping) and the third generation grew from the 1985's until now with its hybrid theories. With the development of implementation theory from each generation, various definitions and understandings of implementation emerge.

Implementation according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary is the same as implementation or implementation. In general, implementation can be interpreted as an action or implementation of a plan that has been carefully and in detail the implementation or implementation (mature). Policy implementation is an important aspect of the entire policy process, without effective implementation, the decisions of policy makers will not be successfully implemented. According to Leo Agustino, Ph.D (2017: 126) in his book on the basics of public policy, he said that policy implementation can simply be interpreted as a process of translating regulations into action. In practice, policy is a process that is so complex that it is not uncommon for it to be filled with politicians because of the intervention of various interests.

According to Purwanto and Sulistyatuti (2012:21) the core implementation is an activity to distribute the policy outputs carried out by the implementers to the target group as an effort to realize the policy. According to Guntur Setiawan (Setiawan, 2004:39) Implementation is the expansion of activities that mutually adjust the process of interaction between goals and actions to achieve them and requires an effective implementation network, bureaucracy. Meanwhile, Howlett and Ramesh (1995:153) define policy implementation as "the process whereby programs or policies are carried out; it is denoted the translation of plans into practice". Where the two definitions are in line with Barrett's (2004:251) writing

which states policy implementation as "translating policy into action" when translated simply means translating policy into action. So, policy implementation is to run the content or content of the policy into the application mandated by the policy itself. The implementation of decisions is usually in the form of laws, but can also take the form of important executive orders or decisions or judicial decisions.

Public policy

According to Leo Agustino, Ph.D (2017:126) in his book on the basics of public policy, he said that public policy is the result of intensive interaction between policy-making actors based on phenomena that must be solved. Not only that, public policies often include public participation in order to produce the best decisions. But not infrequently policies are the result of "work" that is closed. In other words, policy takes place in an undemocratic political context so that decisions are very top-down. Public policy according to Anderson (1990) Dye (1992), as well as Moran, Rein and Goodin (2006), was studied in order to add deeper knowledge about the "policy process". The policy process is a series of paths that need to be passed to understand the symptoms or phenomena that need to be resolved by one or more public policies.

Political Policy

Noam Chomsky, a renowned philosopher from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), said that politics and policy are two things that cannot be separated. Where there is policy, there is political power and policy is two things that cannot be separated, where there is policy, there is political power, interests and political actors who work and form interactions, or sometimes even intersections lead to conflict.

The existence of the political side of a

policy that in practice colors human life wherever they live and are located. Michael Hash (2008), a health consultant from the United States (US), in his speech said that the relationship (intersection) between politics and policy is in that interest and not infrequently between politics and policy goals are two different things. Politics talks about goals such as fighting for values and offices (offices) against political opponents, while policy aims to produce solutions to important problems that need support from those affected by the policy. Drs. AG. Subarsono, M.si., MA in his book on public policy analysis (2015) discusses the importance of public policies that are useful for political purposes; a public policy that is made through the right process with the support of a strong theory has a strong position against criticism from political opponents. Policies exist to convince political opponents who previously did not agree. Such a policy will not be easily repealed just because of a momentary excuse from political opponents.

In this description, it can be concluded that policy and politics are an inseparable unit, because basically the policies issued by the implementers are the products of politics and aim to improve the welfare of society.

Foreign Citizens (WNA)

Foreigner in the Indonesian-English translation dictionary is also defined as strange, foreigner and alien. An alien or foreigner is defined as a person in a country who is not a national of that country. (Safaat, 2008:112) Foreign nationals referred to here are Indonesian citizens who have visited or settled in Timor Leste for a long period of time and have complete documents including visas and passports. The Government of Timor Leste has established laws and regulations that specifically regu-

late human behavior in and out of the national territory of Timor Leste, namely the Immigration and Asylum Law. Timor Leste's immigration laws and regulations issued in the state gazette are the Immigration and Asylum Law No. 9 of 2003. The immigration law regulates the general concept of foreigners, including:

Artigo 1:(1) The current document regulates the conditions of entry, stay, exit and parting of foreigners from national territory;(2) The above does not preclude special agreements set out in international treaties and conventions that the Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste is party to, adheres to, or becomes party to.

This article regulates the presence of foreigners who enter and stay in Timor Leste, the general explanation referred to in article 2 explains that foreigners are people who are not citizens of Timor Leste as follows in article 2 paragraph 1, namely; For the purposes of this instrument, a foreigner is deemed to be anyone who cannot prove his or her East Timorese citizenship. Whereas what is meant by immigration in article 3 provides a definition of foreigners, namely the definition of residents are foreigners who are considered as residents when they have been inherited a place of residence of a legal authority and has been approved with a valid instrument of law.

The Government of Timor Leste has issued a policy regarding visa exemption for Indonesian citizens who wish to go to Timor Leste. This visa-free policy is a reciprocal policy from the Timor Leste government to the Indonesian government. The success of a regulation is largely determined by the implementation process, meaning that implementation is vital because the implementation of a policy runs effectively. Likewise with the implementation of the Timor Leste government's political policy regarding visa exemption for Indonesian citizens.

The above conditions are the basis of the author's interest in conducting research related to visa-free policies for Indonesian citizens, and in accordance with the description and problems that the author has listed in the background. So the author conducted

a research by combining research variables processed by the author, with a simplified framework model by the researcher by taking the 4 variables produced by Van Metter and Van Horn (in Agustino Leo 2017:133-136). The results are as follows:

Figure 2.1. Research Mindset

Research Methodology

Based on the subject matter studied, this research uses a qualitative approach. Qualitative research has main characteristics, which are concerned with meaning, context and in the research process which is more cyclical than linear. With data collection and data analysis taking place simultaneously, more concerned with depth than breadth of research, while the researcher himself is the main instrument. The type of research conducted is descriptive, namely

problem solving procedures investigated by describing the meaning of the topic at hand. In the context of this research, descriptive is explaining or describing the implementation of the East Timor government's political policy regarding visa-free visas for Indonesian citizens in 2019.

Informants from research on the implementation of the Timor Leste government's political policy regarding visa-free visas for Indonesian citizens in 2019. The sources of

information for researchers are; Head of the Mota'ain Cross-border Post, Head of the TPI Class II Immigration Office in Atambua, Head of the Timor Leste Consulate office in Kupang and the people who get VISA-free benefits.

Research Results

Timor Leste Government Policy regarding Visa Exemption for Indonesian Citizens

Public policy (public policy) covers all areas of life related to the public interest or the problems of the people, so that public policy always consists of various choices of attitudes or government decisions that are interconnected with one another. Policy implementation is one of the important aspects of government policy because it relates to how the policies taken can run effectively so that these policies can solve various public problems. The basis of science and studies in public policy is public administration. Where is public administration as defined by Zauhar (2001; 31) that public administration is the organization and management of men and materials to achieve the purposes of government and public administration is the art of science of management as applied affairs of state. is the organization and management of people and materials to achieve the goals of government and public administration is the art of management science as an applied state affair). Zauhar's definition above provides an overview of the main focus of the scientific scope of public administration including state administration, which is related to government and the policies it makes.

To become a policy that regulates the public interest or the problems of the people, there are several characteristics that must be met. Referring to the opinion of Abidin (2012: 23) that there are at least five characteristics of public policy, namely: (1)

public policy is purposive, goal-oriented behavior rather than random or chance behavior. random or coincidental), (2) public policy consists of courses of action rather than separate, discrete decisions, or actions performed by government officials (public policy consists of a series of actions rather than separate decisions or actions taken by government officials),(3) policy is what government do, not what they say will do or what they intend to do(policy is what the government does, not what it wants to do),(4) public policy may either negative or positive(public policy can in the form of negative or positive), (5) public policy is based on law and is authoritative (public policy is based on law). Zauhar's definition above provides an overview of the main focus of the scientific scope of public administration including state administration, which is related to government and policies made. After fulfilling the characteristics mentioned above, then a policy can go through the following stages, as mentioned by Dunn (2004:71) who says that these stages are the agenda setting stage (problem formation), the policy formulation stage (problem formulation).), the stage of policy adoption (policy adaptation), the stage of policy implementation (policy implementation), and the stage of policy evaluation (policy evaluation).

After going through several stages of the public policy-making process mentioned above, then the Timor Leste government's political-free policy regarding visa exemption for Indonesian citizens in 2019), this policy is contained in Government Resolution or Resolucoes do Governo Number 25/2019. Regarding the application of visa-free for Indonesian citizens. Gupta (2021:61-62) states that after a public policy is adopted, then the next step is to implement it. In the process of implementing a policy, according to the Implementor, to

understand the complexity of the policy, it is seen from the environment in which the policy is implemented. The Timor Leste government's policy regarding visa exemption for Indonesian citizens is regulated in Government Resolution or Resolucoes do Governo Number 25/2019 which states that tourist visa exemption is granted for 30 days and can be extended once during the same period. for 60 days.

This regulation eventually became the basis for the government of Timor Leste in implementing a free policy for Indonesian citizens, as one of the policies that have been implemented and can go according to plan, so that the policy is in line with the target. The visa-free policy for Indonesian citizens in its implementation is not just reducing or minimizing the use of rat trails. Moreover, East Nusa Tenggara Province, especially Belu Regency, has four cross-border routes between Indonesia and Timor Leste. So that illegal road access will continue. Apart from the illegal route, the visa-free policy for Indonesian citizens is also a policy of reciprocity or reciprocity for Timor-Leste, for the policy of exempting East Timorese tourist visas to Indonesia (Berly Martawardaya, Ari Rakatama, Dhenny Yuartha Junifta & Dinda Ayu Maharani, 2022).

A public policy (public policy) is basically made to solve problems that intersect with the interests and needs of the public (society). Even if a policy is made by the state or government, public policy must be aligned and directed at seeking the essence of the public interest, which in its formulation effort is framed with a conventional approach that displays its elastic character, namely the state as the main actor in presenting a policy construction capable of accommodate the essence by placing the public (society) as the main actor in it (Wing Thye Woo & Chang Hong, 2010).

The performance of policy implementation can be measured by the level of success if and only if the size and objectives of the policy are realistic with the socio-culture that exists at the level of implementing the policy. When the size of the policy or policy objectives are too ideal (even too utopian) to be implemented at the citizen level, it will be difficult to realize public policies to the point that it can be said to be successful.

Van Metter and Van Horn discuss several elements that may affect an organization in implementing policies such as the competence and size of an agency's staff, the level of hierarchical control over decisions, sub-units and processes within the implementing agency, and the political resources of an organization. The attitude of acceptance or rejection of the implementing (agent) will greatly affect the success or failure of the performance of public policy implementation. Community participation in the implementation of the policy is the most important part in the implementation of the visa-free policy, besides the key lies in the implementer as the implementer of the policy but also the community as the recipient of the visa-free policy needs to be actively involved and actively involved in the policies implemented so that the policy can run well.

The economic, social and political environment is the most important part in the smooth running of a policy. The economic environment will basically increase state revenues, and the social environment will also support the smooth implementation of the visa-free policy and the last one is the political environment, where in implementing this policy implementation the political environment is very necessary because it relates to the two countries. To find out whether the economic, social and political conditions were implemented well or not, the researcher interviewed Mr. Jesuino Dos Reis Matos C as the head of the Consulate

on Thursday 8 June 2020 saying that:

"From a political and economic point of view, this visa-free policy is presented to strengthen both sides, namely the political side and the economic side, from the political side we can see from the good relations between Timor Leste and Indonesia. issued by the Indonesian government has been welcomed by the Timor Leste government and this relationship continues well. And from an economic point of view, this visa-free policy is solely to attract the attention of tourists who want to travel in Timor Leste, thereby increasing the country's income".

Furthermore, the researcher continued the interview with Mr. Aderito Baptista Lopes on Friday 8 June 2021 saying that.

"For the political side, of course, to strengthen bilateral relations between the two countries and for the economic side, namely to develop the economy in the field of tourism. And for the social side, it is seen from the cultural, religious background, and of course because of family ties. And please note that the types of visas that are freed are visit visas and other visas remain in force and if the period has expired must be reported and paid according to the types of visas"

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the implementation of the visa - free policy has been going well . This is what the researchers got while conducting research while in the field. (a). Based on the elements that serve as benchmarks for researchers, several conclu-

sions can be drawn: (1) Size and objectives: this visa-free policy is a reciprocal policy given by the government of Timor Leste to Indonesia, and the purpose of this policy is to mutually build relations (2) The attitude or trend of implementing: the implementation of the visa-free policy is technically said to be good, such as achieving efficiency in the size of immigration staff and mota'ain officers having good qualities such as education and work experience.(3) Community Participation: community participation in complying with immigration rules has been going well, seen from the answers that have been conveyed from the immigration authorities and also the people themselves. (b). The supporting and inhibiting factors in the implementation of the visa-free policy are supporting factors: (1) the information carried out by the implementor is conveyed through the print media as the main part. (2) the visa-free policy is a reciprocal policy carried out by the Timor Leste government to the government. Indonesia. (3) The characteristics of the implementor are adequate, both in terms of competence and education. Inhibiting factors: (1) lack of assistance and control in the implementation of visa-free policies so that people are indifferent in carrying out the rules that have been put in place. (2) there is an outbreak of the corona virus which hampers the process of crossing borders between countries. (3) Good communication between the implementor and the recipient of the visa-free policy has not gone well, resulting in miscommunication.

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